

The Impact of Porter's Five Forces in Internet Services Provider (ISP), Myanmar

*Saw Arli Shar¹, Zin Ko Ko², Nan Wai Linn³, Yin Ko Ko⁴

¹Doctorate Degree Scholar, Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) Yangon, Myanmar.

²Founder & Chancellor, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

³Vice Principal & Registrar, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

⁴Director, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

*Corresponding author: **Saw Arli Shar**

Doctorate Degree Scholar, Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) Yangon, Myanmar.

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to use Porter's Five Forces model to assess the impact of the internet service provider (ISP) sector in Myanmar. A survey research design was employed in this study. The study's sample consisted of 117 staff members from the customer support and marketing teams across 10 ISP in Myawaddy, Myanmar as well as 10 managers. Simple random sampling was used in this study to choose the sample. Structured questionnaires were employed to obtain primary data for this investigation. The study used SPSS version 26 to analyze quantitative data, using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. The study's goals were to evaluate the impact of the ISP industry's appeal in Myanmar on the amount of competition that Rivalry Among Existing Firms, Threat of New Entrants, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Bargaining Power of Buyers and Threat of Substitutes.

Keywords: Internet Services Provider (ISP), Porter's Five Forces, ISP industry's, Telecommunications, Competition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Many competitive industries are very difficult to penetrate, despite all the techniques that may be available to utilize. Any firm that is seeking success has to look at the competition and, likewise, be aware of the ways in which competition affects its strategies. A method of analyzing competition is by doing industry analysis. Porter (1980) analyzed the forces influencing competitiveness in an industry and the elements of industry structure. He derived that the foundations of industry structure are the bargaining power of buyers, the bargaining power of suppliers, the threat of new entrants, and the threat of substitute products.

According to Wan and Beil (2009), the core task of a strategist is to comprehend and cope with competition. Although most managers habitually define competition in a narrow sense, they make the assumption that competition only happens among today's direct competitors. Nevertheless, competition for higher profits goes far beyond reputable industry opponents to also include the other four competition forces, which include the bargaining power of suppliers, the threat of potential entrants, the bargaining power of buyers, and the threat of substitute products or services (West, 2009). The comprehensive opposition that has resulted from all five forces helps to describe the industry outline and gives a formation on the nature of competitive relations within a particular industry (Dobbs, 2014).

The telecommunications industry, mainly involving data communications, is increasingly becoming one of the most crucial sectors in any economy. Rapid technological advancements have made it the fastest-paced industry in the world. Developed countries have mastered the speed necessary to keep abreast of the fast-paced nature of the telecommunications industry; however, developing countries significantly lag in this regard. Due to this, there are plenty of opportunities for growth in terms of new markets, increased access to information, and improved efficiency (Wanyama & Baryamureeba, 2007).

Much as the telecommunications industry has a plethora of opportunity, it is curbed by its share of challenges that inhibit full potential actualization. These include a lack of appropriate legal framework, e.g., e-commerce, inadequate national infrastructure to reach markets, mobile operators refusing to interconnect, low information and communication technology (ICT) awareness in the industry, heavy taxes on telecommunication equipment, a limited amount of local content that hinders the growth of the industry, and a lack of capacity to manage growth (Communication Commission of Kenya, 2005).

2. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The study of the historical development, functions, and effects of globalization technology (Duque et al., 2007). They looked into how the diffusion of technology is influenced by socioeconomic and cultural shifts that are particular to each location, explaining why different products are available in various regions of the world. The influx of new competitors and innovative services offered to draw in and keep customers have come to define the competitive landscape; however, the increased level of competition has led to a decline in sales and in the profitability of market participants. Porter's Five Forces model has been used in a few studies to assess the industry's attractiveness to ISPs. A variety of methodologies, industries, and nations' studies have used the five forces model. By examining the impact of Porter's Five Forces on competitive advantage in the ISP industry in Myawaddy, Myanmar, this study aims to close the research gap.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are

1. To assess the Porter's Five Forces of internet service provider industry in Myanmar.
2. To analyze the impact of the forces on attractiveness of the internet service provider industry in Myanmar.

4. METHOD OF STUDY

This research approach is a deductive approach, and it is survey research. It uses a cross-sectional study. Primary data will be collected with simple random sampling. The sample size will be 10 managers and 117 staff of marketing departments and customer service teams in 10 internet service providers in Myanmar. Multiple regression analyses will be undertaken in this study. Structured questionnaires will be used to collect primary data. The 10 ISP that were the subject of this study's Porter's Five Forces analysis, which was limited in Myanmar.

5. Research Design

This study used descriptive research design by using cross sectional study. Descriptive research design is a type of research design that aims to systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. More specifically, it helps answer the what, when, where, and how questions regarding the research problem rather than the why. A cross-sectional study is a type of research design in which researcher collect data from many different individuals at a single point in time. In cross-sectional research, observe variables without influencing them. An analytical cross-sectional study is a type of quantitative, non-experimental research design.

6. Population and Sampling

The target population is the group of individuals that the intervention intends to conduct research in and draw conclusions from.

In this study, the target population is the internet service providers in Myawaddy. Among them, random sample of internet service provider were selected by using sampling random sampling. The survey questionnaires were sent for the research questions to selected sample by using Google Forms.

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

7.1 Internet Service Provider (ISP)

An internet service provider (ISP) is a company that provides access to the internet. ISPs can provide this access through multiple means, including dial-up, DSL, cable, wireless and fiber-optic connections. A variety of companies serve as ISPs, including cable providers, mobile carriers, and telephone companies. A variety of companies serve as ISPs, including cable providers, mobile carriers, and telephone companies. In some cases, a single company may offer multiple types of service (e.g., cable and wireless), while in other cases, a company may focus on just one type of service (e.g., fiber-optic). Without an ISP, individuals and businesses could not reach the internet and the opportunities it provides.

7.2 Porter's Five Forces Model

Porter's Five Forces Model, which uses five competitive forces to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of an industry. In 1979, Michael Porter of Harvard Business School published this model. Here are the names of these five forces:

a) Threat of New Entrants

A company's competitive position will be at risk when new competitors enter an industry offering the same goods or services. If an industry is expanding and simple to enter, competition will rise quickly. Profits start to decrease as more

businesses aggressively compete for market share in the same market. Therefore, established businesses put a lot of effort into making entry barriers prohibitive (Ryu, 2018). Threat of new entrants high when little capital is low, existing companies can't make enough countermove, existing players don't own government authority or license or have established brand reputation, no protection of authorized regulation, low switching cost (it doesn't cost much to switch to other industries), customers loyalty are low, products are nearly standardized, and per unit cost is low (Porter, 2008).

New competitors, in particular, bring resources, a desire to expand their market share, and new capabilities that are not currently available. The degree to which entry is threatened depends on the barriers posed by already available products and the responses that market participants can anticipate from established competitors. The new entrants will obviously not pose a serious threat to entry if the entry barriers are high and new entrants can expect severe retaliation from the incumbent competitors (Porter, 1979). If the situation is reversed, then the current players should be prepared for fierce competition from the new entrants. Industry players keep an eye on the factors that prevent new entrants from accurately estimating market growth, and this information signals the need for them to develop a competitive strategy so they can continue to thrive in this highly competitive market.

b) Bargaining Power of Suppliers

If the suppliers have significant negotiating or monopoly power, they may take unfair advantage of the market by offering their customers monopoly prices or inferior goods. Because they must charge more for goods, it may reduce the dealer companies' profit. Few suppliers serve a large number of customers, suppliers have influence and threaten horizontal integration, there are few substitutes raw materials, resources are limited, and the switching cost for raw materials is particularly high (Porter, 2008). Knowing the number of dealers and their relative clout will help marketers make informed decisions about how to maintain market dominance.

C) Bargaining Power of Buyers

Customers have the power to pressure marketers, which also affects the buyer's attitude toward price changes. This power is also referred to as the market of the results. Businesses can take steps to lessen the power of the consumer, such as using customer retention techniques. The volume of purchases has an impact on how much consumers can influence market forces (Solomon and Rabolt, 2004).

Powerful customers gain more benefits by exerting pressure on vendors to lower prices, demanding top-notch services, and attacking vendors back at any cost to business productivity (Smith, 2004). Consumers are dominant if they have greater bargaining power than business players, especially if they are price conscious and use their power to primarily drive down prices. Different customer groups' negotiating power can vary greatly as a result of connected suppliers (Solomon).

They have more negotiating power when there are fewer consumers or when they buy an excessive amount of goods relative to the seller's capacity (Wan and Beil, 2009). High customer volume is crucial for businesses in industries with high fixed costs. Low incremental costs and high start-up costs force the investor to cover their investment through declining prices (West, 2009).

(d) Threats of Substitutes

Threats of substitutes are the other force. When consumers are able to switch from one good or service to another at little or no cost, they are especially vulnerable to this force (Porter, 2008). They can easily find alternatives with more favorable prices or higher quality. The price variable will be the main issue. Customers' willingness to pay for a product is partially influenced by the availability of alternatives. Due to comparative consumer price insensitivity and inelastic demand in response to price, there are no close substitute products available. In response to the price increase, customers will switch to alternatives because there are close substitute products available.

(e) Rivalry Among Existing Firms

The competition between already-existing competitors in the industry is the other force. The most crucial element in determining a company's competitive position in a given industry is its power. Low profits are the result of the aggressive return competition among businesses in the competitive sector. In some circumstances, there is fierce competition between businesses due to a high number of rivals, high barriers to exit, undifferentiated products that are easy to switch, equal size of competitors, and low customer loyalty (Porter, 2008).

The degree of competition in a particular economic sector is influenced by a variety of factors. The number of competitors in the industry makes up the first component. An intense rivalry will exist if the industry has a lot of competitors. Market share or competitor size is another factor. The degree of competition also rises if the rivals are comparable in terms of market share and size (Elms et al., 2010). The rate of industry growth is another element influencing the level of competition in a corporate sector. When growth is slow, competition intensifies significantly. Start-up costs are another factor; if they are high, there will be intense competition to offset those high costs.

Differentiating products from one another is a key component as well. The level of competition will be high if the products in the goods and services sectors are fundamentally the same. The following crucial variables are switching costs and brand loyalty. Competition within the industry will increase if buyer switching costs are low and customer loyalty to the brand is irrelevant (Bridwell and Chun-Jui, 2005). The variety of competitors is the other factor. The rivalry within the industry will become more intense if competitors adopt diverse tactical strategies by positioning themselves in a different way from the rest of their rivals. The firm's capacity is the additional factor. If a sector of the economy has excess production capacity, there will be fierce competition. Barriers to exit are the following component. There will be fierce competition between the competing firms when the startup costs are high. Even if all of the aforementioned conditions are negatively affected, the level of competition will decrease. For instance, low levels of rivalry between existing businesses are indicated by factors like few competing firms, an unanticipated market, high industry growth, low start-up costs, highly customizable goods and services, brand loyalty, high switching costs, low manufacturing capacity, competitor similarity, and an easy exit barrier (Davis et al., 2006).

8. Conceptual Framework of the Study

This study is underpinned by Porter five forces theory (1980). This study mainly focusses to analysis the attractiveness of internet service provider company in Myanmar. As shown in figure, five factors that determinant of attractiveness are rivalry among firms, threat of Rivalry Among Existing Firms, Threat of New Entrants, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Bargaining Power of Buyers and Threat of Substitutes. These forms the independent variables of the study. The dependent variable is the attractiveness of internet service provider industry in Myawaddy, Myanmar. Figure 1 shows conceptual model on the relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

1) Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Porter (1980)

9. IMPACT OF PORTER'S FIVE FORCES (The five forces model)

9.1 Impact of Rivalry Among Existing Firms

Five questions were used in this study to examine how people perceived competition among internet service provider companies. Table 9.1 below displays the survey results of respondents' perceptions.

Table 9.1 Impact of Rivalry among Competing Firms

No.	Description	Frequency (%)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	A few numbers of competitors make competitiveness of the industry.	6 (4.8)	22 (17.6)	21 (16.8)	46 (36.8)	30 (24.0)
2.	The market is growing fast, so this industry is competitiveness.	3 (2.4)	3 (2.4)	14 (11.2)	73 (58.4)	32 (25.6)
3.	High fixed cost makes ISPs to exit difficult from industry.	1 (0.8)	14 (11.2)	26 (20.8)	58 (46.4)	26 (20.8)
4.	The level of rivalry in market segment affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	2 (1.6)	15 (12.0)	15 (12.0)	67 (53.6)	26 (20.8)
5.	Hunting the qualified employee by other ISPs affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	6 (4.8)	29 (23.2)	16 (12.8)	47 (37.6)	27 (21.6)

It was discovered that 85.2 percent of respondents (including 46.4 percent and 20.8 percent) agreed more favorably that ISPs' inability to exit the industry is a result of high fixed costs. Then, 84% of respondents (including 58% and 25.6%) agreed more favorably that the market is expanding quickly and that this sector is competitive. Additionally, 74.4 percent of respondents (including 53.6 and 20.8 percent) agree more strongly that the degree of competition in a given market segment affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry. However, it is evident that 59.2 percent of respondents (including 37.6 percent and 21.6%) only concur that the recruitment of qualified workers by rival ISPs reduces the industry's ability to compete.

9.2 Impact of Threat of New Entrants

In this study, seven questions were used to examine how people perceived the threat posed by new internet service providers. The perception of survey respondents is depicted in Table 9.2 below.

Table 9.2 Impact of Threat of New Entrants

No.	Description	Frequency (%)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Customers are loyal to their brand so, this industry is competitiveness.	4 (3.2)	23 (18.4)	24 (19.2)	39 (31.2)	35 (28.0)
2.	The emerging of new ISPs allowed By MCIT affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	2 (1.6)	6 (4.8)	20 (16.0)	58 (46.4)	39 (31.2)
3.	High fixed costs make barriers to entry.	3 (2.4)	18 (14.4)	27 (21.6)	53 (42.4)	24 (19.2)
4.	Unique Assets of firms make barriers to entry.	4 (3.2)	29 (23.2)	23 (18.4)	45 (36.0)	24 (19.2)
5.	Complex process to run firms is also threat for new entrants.	2 (1.6)	31 (24.8)	22 (17.6)	45 (36.0)	25 (20.0)
6.	Acquiring customer is also a threat of new entrant for new competitors.	3 (2.4)	28 (22.4)	22 (17.8)	47 (37.6)	25 (20.0)
7.	For Achieving authorized licenses is challenges for new competitor.	4 (3.2)	20 (16.0)	29 (23.2)	45 (36.0)	27 (21.6)

The development of new ISPs permitted by MCIT has been found to affect the competitiveness of the ISP industry, according to 77.6 percent of respondents (including 46.4 percent and 31.2 percent). Furthermore, 61.6 percent of respondents (including 42.4 percent and 19.2 percent) are more in agreement that their company's high fixed costs serve as entry barriers. Additionally, 59.2 percent (including 31.2 percent and 28 percent) of respondents are more in agreement that the majority of consumers are brand loyal, which makes this industry competitive. However, it can be seen that 55 percent of respondents (including 36 percent and 19 percent) only concur that businesses with particular assets that prevent competitors from entering the market have barriers to entry.

9.3 Perception on Bargaining Power of Suppliers

In this study, five questions were used to investigate how people perceived the bargaining power of suppliers to internet service providers. Below, in Table 9.3, are the survey results of respondents' perceptions.

Table 9.3 Impact of Bargaining Power of Suppliers

No.	Description	Frequency (%)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	Suppliers are important stakeholders in this industry and playing a critical role in growing the industry.	1 (0.8)	7 (5.6)	15 (12.0)	61 (48.8)	41 (32.8)
2.	Switching cost to change suppliers is high, so most firms sticking to existing suppliers.	3 (2.4)	28 (22.4)	16 (12.8)	49 (39.2)	29 (23.2)
3.	The market is dominated by a few large suppliers.	1 (0.8)	24 (19.2)	22 (17.6)	51 (40.8)	27 (21.6)
4.	The number of local ISPs relying on A given supplier affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	4 (3.2)	23 (18.4)	17 (13.6)	60 (48.0)	21 (16.8)
5.	The bandwidth support from the Suppliers is important for ISP business.	3 (2.4)	5 (4.0)	18 (14.4)	44 (35.2)	55 (44.0)

It can be seen that 81 percent of respondents (including 48 percent and 32 percent) are more in agreement that suppliers are growing to be significant stakeholders in the industry and playing a key role in its restructuring and future development. Additionally, 79.2 percent of respondents (including 35.2 percent and 44 percent) are more in agreement that the suppliers' support for bandwidth is crucial for ISP operations. Additionally, 64.8 percent of respondents (including 48 percent and 16.8 percent) are more in agreement that the number of regional ISPs that depend on a particular supplier has an impact on the competitiveness of the ISP industry. Despite this, it was discovered that 62.4 percent of respondents (including 39.2 percent and 23.2 percent) agreed that they preferred to stick with certain suppliers because doing so would incur high switching costs.

9.4 Impact of Bargaining Power of Buyers

In this study, five questions were used to examine how internet service provider customers perceived their bargaining power. Table 9.4 below displays the survey results of respondents' perception.

Table 9.4 Impact of Bargaining Power of Buyers

No.	Description	Frequency (%)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	There are many customers for firms so, they have not bargained power.	35 (28.0)	37 (29.6)	25 (20.0)	25 (20.0)	3 (2.4)
2.	Value the customer requirement and providing a promotion affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	7 (5.6)	32 (25.6)	19 (15.2)	33 (26.4)	34 (27.2)
3.	Value the customer suggestion affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	1 (0.8)	12 (9.6)	21 (16.8)	53 (42.4)	38 (30.4)
4.	Customers' demands make it competitive.	4 (3.2)	11 (8.8)	20 (16.0)	50 (40.0)	40 (32.0)
5.	The power of customers influences the prices that we charge for internet service.	4 (3.2)	12 (9.6)	18 (14.4)	50 (40.0)	41 (32.8)

According to the survey results, 72.8 percent of respondents—including 40 and 32.8 percent of those who participated—agreed or strongly agreed that customer power affects the prices we charge for internet service. Finally, 72.8 percent of respondents (including 42.4 percent and 30.4 percent) are more in agreement that the ISP industry's ability to compete is impacted by how much it values customer suggestions. Additionally, 72 percent of respondents—including 40 percent and 32 percent—agreed more strongly that the demands of the consumer drive competition. However, it can be seen that

22.4 percent of respondents (including 20 percent and 22.4 percent) only concur that they have enough customers in larger markets and that customers are not a key component of attractiveness.

9.5 Impact of Threat of Substitutes

Seven questions were used in this study to examine people's perceptions of the Threat of substitute services from internet service providers. Table 9.5 below displays the survey results of respondents' perception.

Table 9.5 Impact of Threat of Substitutes

No.	Description	Frequency (%)				
		1	2	3	4	5
1.	The customers are loyal to existing service providers.	9 (7.2)	27 (21.6)	26 (20.8)	39 (31.2)	24 (19.2)
2.	Our services compare favorably to possible substitutes.	1 (0.8)	8 (6.4)	23 (18.4)	51 (40.8)	42 (33.6)
3.	High switch cost for customers to take another service.	2 (1.6)	15 (12.0)	33 (26.4)	45 (36.0)	30 (24.0)
4.	Availability of data SIM affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	8 (6.4)	37 (29.6)	18 (14.4)	36 (28.8)	26 (20.8)
5.	Availability of satellite connection affects the competitiveness of the ISP industry.	7 (5.6)	21 (16.8)	28 (22.4)	43 (34.4)	26 (20.8)
6.	Substitute products restrict the market share of the industry	4 (3.2)	18 (14.4)	21 (16.8)	55 (44.0)	27 (21.6)
7.	Substitute products hinder product Or service differentiation among customers.	2 (1.6)	10 (8.0)	23 (18.4)	57 (45.6)	33 (26.4)

It is discovered that 74 percent of respondents—including 40 percent and 33 percent—agree or more that their services compare favorably to potential substitutes. Additionally, 72% of respondents (including 45.6 percent and 26.4 percent) are more in agreement that substitute products make it harder for customers to differentiate between different products or services. Then, 65.6% (including 44.6% and 21.6%) concur that substitute products put a cap on the prices we can profitably charge, limiting the industry's potential returns. However, it was discovered that 50% of respondents (including 31% and 19%) agreed that customers remained loyal to their current service providers.

10. CONCLUSIONS

The study uses descriptive analyze the competitive forces (Porter's Five Forces) of an organization. Respondents agree on market segments, industry competition, and high fixed costs in the ISP industry. They also support restructuring critical roles and supplier selection. They also consider customer suggestions, competitive demands, and internet service costs. They believe substitute products are difficult to differentiate and attribute profitability to industry competition. According to the average perception values for each factor, it is discovered that the majority of respondents are in greater agreement with Rivalry Among Existing Firms, Threat of New Entrants, Bargaining Power of Suppliers, Bargaining Power of Buyers and Threat of substitutes. when examining the industry's attractiveness, the majority of respondents are more in favor of higher substitute product prices, the absence of monopoly power, and the competitiveness of the ISP sector due to the inferior quality of substitute products, the impact of porter's five forces in internet services provider (ISP), Myanmar.

11. RECOMMENDATIONS

To develop their strategic options, ISP providers need to forge strong bonds with their suppliers. By enhancing resources, updating and substituting programs, and improving the product's quality, ISPs can defeat the forces of suppliers and attract customers. With this new perspective, the Porter's Five Forces, which steer industry competition, have altered organizational structure and procedure. ISP providers should develop their own replacements using a variety of programs or a group of joint programs created by integrating providers to respond to external forces. Providers can reduce the threat of substitutes and raise the barriers for entry by offering self-produced materials. The return and profitability of an organization are determined by the bargaining power of the customer. ISP providers must therefore have a customer retention strategy and a loyalty program.

12. REFERENCES

1. Bridwell, L., & Chun-Jui, K. (2005). An Analysis Of The Computer Industry In China And JTaiwan Using Michael Porter's Determinants Of National Competitive Advantage. *Competitiveness Review*, 15(2), pp. 116-120
2. Davis, E. E., Freedman, M., Lane, J., McCall, B., Nestoriak, N., & Park, T. (2006). Supermarket Human Resource Practices and Competition from Mass Merchandisers. *American Jtheirnal Of Agricultural Economics*, 88(5), pp. 1289- 1295.
3. Dobbs, M. E. (2014). Guidelines for applying Porter's five forces framework: a set of industry analysis templates. *Competitiveness Review*, pp. 32-45
4. Duque, R., Collins, M., Abbate, J., Azambuja, C.C. & Snaprud, M., (2007). Past, Present and Future of Research in the Information Society. Pp. 33-45, DOI: 10.1007/978-0-387- 47650- 6_3
5. Elms, J., Canning, C., de Kervenoael, R., Whysall, P. & Hallsworth, R. (2010). 30 years of retail change: where (and how) do you shop?, *International Jtheirnal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 38(11/12), pp. 817 – 827
6. [https://www.verizon.com/about/blog/isp-meaning#:~:text=An%20internet%20service%20provider%20\(ISP\)%20is%20a%20company%20that%20provides,mobile%20carriers%2C%20and%20telephone%20companies](https://www.verizon.com/about/blog/isp-meaning#:~:text=An%20internet%20service%20provider%20(ISP)%20is%20a%20company%20that%20provides,mobile%20carriers%2C%20and%20telephone%20companies).
7. Porter, M. E. (1980). *Competitive Strategy: Techniques for analyzing industries and Competitors*, New York. Free Press. Porter, M.E. (1985). *Competitive advantage*. New York: Free press.
8. Porter, M.E. (1980). *Competitive Strategy*. New York: Free Press Porter, M.E. (1985). *Competitive Advantage*. New York: Free Press
9. Porter, M.E. (2004). The five competitive forces that shape strategy.. *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 79-84
10. Porter, M.E. (2008). The five competitive forces that shape strategy. *Harvard Business Review*. 86-104.
11. Ryu, M. H. (2018). The Value Co-Creation Strategy for Telecommunication Carriers: Focusing on the Assessment of Potential Strategic Alliance Partners. *Procedia Computer Science*, 139, 338-346.
12. Saw Arli Shar (2003), attractiveness of internet service provider industry in myawaddy
13. Smith, H. (2004). Supermarket Choice and Supermarket Competition in Market Equilibrium. *Review Of Economic Studies*, 71(1), pp. 235-263.
14. Solomon, M. & Rabolt, N. (2004). *Consumer Behavior in Fashion*, Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall
15. Wan, Z., & Beil, D. R. (2009). Bargaining Power and Supply Base Diversification. *Working Papers (Faculty) -- University Of Michigan Business School*.
16. West, D. S. (2009). Evaluating a supermarket relocation strategy using spatial competition analysis.. *Annals of Regional Science*.
17. Wanyama T. & Baryamureeba V., (2007). Increased adoption of ICT in the private sector often leads to expanded growth by opening new markets, increasing access to market information & n improving Efficiency. *International Journal of Computing and ICT Research*, Vol. 1, pg56, June 2007. ISSN 1818-1139.